

Brasilia Reproduced as Backdrop

"Boys, boys come here will you. Look who's coming on the street, all dressed up in modernistic style. It ain't nobody but..." (Aunt Hagar's Blues, played by Ted Lewis and his band, w/ Jimmy Dorsey on the clarinet)."(Lispector, 1989: 138)

In 1964, Clarice Lispector wrote the short essay "Five Days in Brasilia", in which she ironically evoked a fashion runway to describe the monumentality of Brazil's new capital. It is unlikely that she suspected that this characterization would foretell Brasilia's rebirth as an ultra-hip fashion statement more than thirty years later in the international press.¹ For Lispector, Oscar Niemeyer, and Lucio Costa, indeed for the national and architectural imaginary of the 1960's, the sculptural forms of the monumental axis occupied center stage, perspectively framed against an endless horizon. While Lispector's fashion reference may seem irreverent to the national aspirations that the architecture was meant to embody, her essay did place the architectural object squarely in the foreground, not unlike Niemeyer's sketches which feature numerous admiring eyes (figure 1). In recent fashion magazines, though, it is no longer the architecture that is the recipient of this adulation – Brasilia's monuments move to the background and become the landscape and horizon that frames the adorned subject in clothes that either contrast or compliment the shapes and shadows of the concrete (figure 2).

fig. 1

fig. 2

How can we account for this shift and why might it be at all important to explore? Indeed, one might easily dismiss these layouts as stemming from the stylistic revival of a mid-century aesthetic. However, Brasilia's polemical and historical role in the formation of Brazilian Nationhood suggests we examine this phenomenon as something more than the latest fad in menswear. I would like to suggest in this very short paper, that a positional shift in Brasilia's representation from foreground to background has occurred in these fashion shots. This reflects a perceptual shift where Brasilia's architecture moves beyond the realm of national *symbol* and becomes, a *scape*, or field, connected to interests of the global market. Consequently, the *cultural commodity* becomes subject to the *temporal* model of value on which fashion relies. From these shifts we might ask if this commercial appropriation of Brasilia's monuments results from something inherent in its architecture that reflects the conflicting desires of the post-colonial state to operate internationally while resisting internationalization, or if it is a natural consequence of globalization that threatens all national cultural products.

From the symbolic to the scapic

The emergence of a capital from scratch in three years was a "promise" to Brazil and the world of impending national prosperity and economic power. This Utopian gesture was grounded less in ideology or a call for order, but in a hope for the future - a national promise. Hope was central to Oscar Niemeyer's Utopianism, which set aside the goal of reframing society and placed architecture in the realm of art.

"I am in favor of an almost unlimited plastic freedom...things that are new and beautiful capable of arousing surprise and emotion by their very newness and creativeness...designed above all to withdraw the visitor, be it for a few brief instants, from the difficult problems, at times overwhelming, that life poses for all of us (Niemeyer, 1959: 8)."

Niemeyer's sketch of the National Cathedral in Brasilia, features the omnipresent viewer, represented by multitudinous eyes. Their focus is on the architecture which is emphasized as an object framed, viewed, and admired (figure 3). As seen in both the drawing and the quote, Niemeyer saw the architecture as an autonomous sculptural work that could consequently transport the "Brazilian" viewer from her/his daily struggles into an aesthetically-inspired ephemeral dreamworld. The artistic intention of the architect was complimented by the intention of the state where the capital buildings were associated with the aspirations and fortitude of the Nation. In Lucio Costa's competition proposal for the city, there is a clear consideration of the physical and visual relation between the Brazilian subject and the architecture, and the consolidation of national solidarity this relationship establishes amongst a truly heterogeneous population:

"One-way traffic forces the buses to make a detour leaving the road under the platform; this gives the travelers their last view of the monumental radial artery before the bus enters the residential radial artery, and is a psychologically satisfactory way of saying farewell to the national Capital (Costa, 1957: 23)."

"Nation" as a constructed entity is something quite illusory, but an identifiable object/icon can begin to condense its multiple ethnicities, histories, and languages. George Bataille once stated that "the national monument silences us by imposing the majesty and authority to any confusion (Bataille, 1971: 171). The intentional foregrounding of Brasilia's architecture by Niemeyer and Costa empowered it with symbolic potential, as the State strove to unite its population on a shared physical, psychological, and experiential terrain.

In these fashion layouts forty years after the city's conception, it is Brasilia's architecture, not the Brazilian nation, that becomes the terrain. The example I use is from a 1996 issue of *The New York Times Magazine* entitled "Reviving the Look of the Future" (Bryan, 1996: 37-48). In this layout (figure 4), the monuments move to the background and become a landscape (figures 5,6). Building and ground surfaces merge together to form a continuous though changing topography (figure 7,8). The architecture

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flows outside the frame of the photo and is walked on rather than looked at. In contrast, the architectural elements that are associated with circulation are emphasized as being disembodied from the body of the building and become random events in the landscape rather than emphasizing a formal architectural sequence (figures 9,10). Actually, the overexposed nature of the photos emphasizes the large swaths of shadows, and the defined edges of the building begin to dissolve. Finally, while Niemeyer and Costa relied on the horizon to frame the architectural object, that horizon is often slanted in these

photos to confuse the horizontal and vertical, and the stability that architecture, bound by gravity implies (figure 11). Indeed, the symbolic building is no longer the framed object of focus. That position has been usurped by the mobile, accessorized male who is no longer identifiably Brazilian. Indeed, anything that is nationally identifiable, flags, symbols, etc. inhabits either shadow or the distant horizon. In its shift from the symbolically specific to the fluidly scapic, the Brasilia backdrop reads more as a futuristic frontier that only the most mobile, international, and cosmopolitan subject can occupy.

Arjun Appadurai has used the word *scapic* (Appadurai, 1997: 32-33) to characterize the multiple global cultural flows that are fed by the movement of global capital. These scapes, or flows, whether they are comprised of media, technology, finance, or ethnicity, are fluid in shape, continually overlapping, and troubling to any notion of boundary. Naturally, the flows of global capital present a distinct challenge to the integrity of the Nation and its desire to consolidate its own fluid diversity into a definable, stable entity. Brasilia's monuments were valued by the state for their ability to project to a national social body. Therefore, these buildings became important cultural commodities both as innovative pieces of architecture and as national symbols. The integrity of this architectural symbolism that embodied a Brazilian Utopianism was important in legitimizing the strength of the Nation.

With the increased pressures of globalization disrupting discreet nationhood, comes a challenge to the integrity and value of national cultural commodities like Brasilia's architecture. Indeed, the manner in which value is focused on objects, whether that value is couched in consumer demand or cultural importance, can be rethought. If we return to the fashion ads, it is the backdrop that contextualizes and gives value to the clothes of the subject. However, the models are not associated with Brazil, and the buildings are not exalted for their architectural ingenuity, or the ingenuity of the Nation that produced them. Rather, the capital is represented as a global frontier - a futuristic landscape that requires both time and mobility to reach. It is this association with remoteness suggested by the backdrop that frames and values the advertised products. Consequently, the commodity is no longer the culturally specific object, but the time and mobility required to temporarily inhabit this frontier. The elevation of the temporal and the mobile, - or the leisure time and resources required for such a lifestyle - presents an alternative system of commodification to the notion of permanence and cultural depth that both the built architectural object and the State strive to project.

Global pressures and the vulnerability of the architectural object

The disintegration of Brasilia's architectural objects into the background as fashionably futuristic moments on a broader global stage raises another question. Is there something about Brasilia's architecture that makes it vulnerable, or ideal for, a fashion backdrop, or are all cultural products susceptible to appropriation and decontextualization on the global market? I would argue that there is an inherent quality to Brasilia's monuments that allow them to be appropriated for purposes other than their original intention. Since we began with Clarice Lispector's processional description, and since we are talking about clothes, I will continue this line of thought with Roberto DaMatta's problematic, though useful, comparison of the costumes and rituals of the Brazilian Independence Day Parade with those of the Brazilian Carnival (DaMatta: 1990, 39-68). On one hand, DaMatta describes the military parade as a spectacle that one observes, that reinforces ideas of hierarchy, that unifies and orders a group for a common nationalistic purpose, and that occurs on a date of historical significance - memorializing a moment that contributed to the development of the modern state. The parade strives to consolidate a population into a singular cohesive social and national body. Carnival, on the other hand, is a spectacle of interaction, moving bodies, hierarchical inversion, that projects stories, qualities, and aspirations unassociated with national historical time. Carnival's spatial flow extends the limits of the individual body, blending it into a heterogeneous social topography.

If, like Lispector, we examine Brasilia's buildings as a type of spatial event, we can see that Brasilia can project qualities of both the national specificity and fortitude of the military parade, and the "hope" and fluidity that is provided by the Carnival parade. It is in the negotiation of these desires that rests the vulnerability of the national cultural product to aesthetic and commercial appropriation beyond national borders. On one hand, the buildings' monumentality and their position on the Cartesian axis assert the authority of the state and the power of the nation. As seen in Niemeyer's sketches, they were designed with an intention of formal frontality, reinforcing shared civic plazas. At the scale of the monumental axis the buildings compose an organized field, assertive and rigid hierarchically and spatially. However, the scale of this gesture undermines its own authority through the gaps between the architectural objects. These gaps provide a station point from which these buildings to be redefined through the lens of the fashion camera. The images emphasize the buildings' fluid character

as a series of surfaces and "un-frames" it from the logic of its urban position, its monumental purpose, and the support of a clear horizon line. Furthermore, Brasilia is not legitimated in a referentially constructed history, as is Washington DC (Tafari, 1979: 30-40), but in a more illusory promise as a nation of the future. Its formal association with the future situates the architecture in a more a universal, or cosmic, notion of time, and not the historical chronology of the Brazilian Nation. Dislodged from a national association, the architecture's representational shift shows how this potential can be mined, and re-positioned, to augment global mechanisms of culture. The capital can easily shift from symbolically representative of the Brazilian nation, to more universal architectural associations with the Future, even if these formal and aesthetic associations are, at heart, historical - ie. the title of the article "Reviving the Look of the Future."

To build his capital, Juscelino Kubitschek not only had to convince his people, but also, the world. Therefore, the city had to navigate the pressures of being both internationally modern with a nationally specific.² The international scrutiny of a national capital, especially of a country with the expectations of Brazil creates such a condition. The changing nature of Brasilia's representation within Brazil is an equally interesting concern, that likely reflects cultural shifts specific independent from the topic discussed in this paper. Indeed, with the Ministry of Education and the Brazil Pavilion in the 1939 World's Fair architectural projections of Brazil that differed depending on their context, national or international, existed almost simultaneously (Bald, 2000: 63-64). However, as the national and international become more intertwined, and, as capital flows more freely, objects that were meant to project the permanence and majesty of a nation, can become topographic embellishments for products with a seasonal life span. While we have looked at Brasilia's architecture as an aesthetic backdrop, this phenomenon is symptomatic of the global flows of culture, technology, people, and capital that use nations as temporal ports. While, one might argue that these flows are overwhelmingly powerful, the use of Brasilia to stage the latest in Western couture also reveals the illusory nature of both the Nation, and the architecture that foregrounds itself as the focal point for the national imaginary.

NOTES

¹ While I concentrate on a layout from a 1996 issue of *The New York Times Magazine*, similar uses of Brasilia can be found in recent issues of *Wallpaper*, the April 2000 issue of the French magazine *BIG*, and the 2000 ad campaign for the Italian shoe designer Sergio Rossi.

² Lucio Costa was acutely aware of this need for both national capital and international city in his continual referencing of great European capitals in his competition proposal of 1957. See, Lucio Costa, "Plano Piloto do Brasilia," *Modulo*, no. 18, 18-31.

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KEYWORDS

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